

UPDATE ON THE PHOTOGRAPHIC IDENTIFICATION GUIDES

We are making good progress with the PHOTO IDENTIFICATION GUIDES. Twenty families have been completed and released. The completed guides are distributed to people that asked for their names to be put on the mailing list. The completed guides will also be available from the end of October on the AFRAS website at <http://afras.ufs.ac.za>. The main purpose for these guides is to provide the latest information on South African spiders and to provide resources for people to correctly identify specimens.

We decided to provide the information in a PDF format to accommodate taxonomic changes. Each version can be updated as new information becomes available. Eventually, we would like to publish these guides as e-books.

In each guide, we provide all the presently known information on 72 families, 480 genera and all of the 2244 presently known South African species. For each of these taxa, at least a page or more is provided, with the following information:

- Common name.
- Morphology (families and genera).
- Type localities and date of description of each species .
- Global distribution.
- Distribution in South Africa; this includes published records and specimens housed in curated collections. Data are listed by province, and localities with coordinates are provided.
- From this data, the AEO (area of occupancy), EOO (extent of occurrence) and altitudinal range (meters above sea level) were determined.
- Assessment for the IUCN Red List, with reference to species of conservation concern (i.e. Rare, Critically Endangered, Endangered and Vulnerable).
- Other criteria: a species may be considered to be of Least Concern (LC) when it has a wide distribution and there is no danger that all populations will be threatened with extinction; Data Deficient (DD/DDT), when more surveys and taxonomic research need to be undertaken; or Not evaluated (NE), when it has not been assessed, as in the case of new, undescribed species.
- Lifestyle includes notes on their behaviour and preferred habitat.
- Conservation measures: indicating if there are known threats; if a species already receive protection in a protected area. Recommendation on what still needs to be done.
- Taxonomic status: here we indicate if the taxon has been revised and whether both sexes are known.
- Literature list: All data provided is supported with scientific references.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION PROVIDED FOR EACH SPECIES:

- A map to show its distribution in South Africa.
- Published illustrations of the genitalia and habitus of each species (if available).
- Images of specimens taken under a microscope.
- Photographs of live specimens (if available), with credits to photographers.

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THE AUTHORS

Prof Charles Haddad (University of the Free State) sampled and identified large datasets and published extensively. As a taxonomist, he provided data on several families.

Prof Stefan Foord (University of Venda) sampled and published extensively, provided data on some taxa, and assisted with the conservation assessments. He prepared the AEO, EOO and maps.

Dr Leon Lotz (retired from National Museum Bloemfontein) sampled and identified large datasets and published extensively. He made the specimen data of the National Museum available for the Guides. He is making a valuable contribution in editing the final guides.

Prof Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman (Emeritus researcher ARC and adjunct professor University of Venda and Pretoria) compiles and manages all the information as the project manager of SANSA.

Additional authors will be invited to contribute when dealing with families that they are the known specialists of, e.g. Amaurobiidae (R. Jocqué for *Chumma*).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI) Threatened Species Programme; the Universities of the Free State, Venda and Pretoria; the National Research Foundation (NRF) for their generous funding and support. The staff of the Arachnology section at the National Collection of Arachnida (Robin Lyle, Petro Marais, Connie Anderson, Sma Mathebula, Annette van den Berg and Jonas Nkwana), as well as several volunteers from the public and the Spider Club of Southern Africa, are thanked for the specimens collected and curated during the SANSA surveys. We also thank the South African National Parks and E. Oppenheimer & Son for support, and providing the opportunity to collect in their parks and reserves, as well as the provincial conservation agencies for collecting permits. We are **especially thankful** to all the >200 photographers who provided photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum. Without their contribution these guides would have not been possible. A special word of thanks to **Peter Webb** for his contribution in collecting and photographing spiders; without his photos these guides would not possible.

The guides are “crowd reviewed”, and a special thanks to Astri Leroy and Len de Beer for their reviews, as well many others for their input.

WHAT WE HOPE TO ACCOMPLISH

All of the species listed on the National Species list are being evaluated again and the present numbers of spiders known from South Africa are 72 families, 480 genera and 2244 species. During the process we flag:

- Genera that still need to be revised.
- Species that are only known from one sex or juveniles.
- Species that are not yet listed on the World Spider Catalog (2020) for South Africa.
- Species that are Data Deficient (DD) needs additional collecting, or Data Deficient for Taxonomic purposes (DDT) that require redescription.
- Species that are listed of special concern, to indicate where more collecting and protection are needed.
- New species that need to be described.

New eresid Photo C.Haddad

WHAT WE HAVE ALREADY ACCOMPLISHED

The following families have been completed. Copies can be obtained from Ansie at DippenaarA@arc.agric.za.

FAMILY	NO PAGES	FAMILY	NO PAGES
AGELENIDAE	23	DEINOPIIDAE	16
AMAUROBIIDAE	26	DICTYNIDAE	14
AMMOXENIDAE	20	DRYMUSIDAE	10
ANAPIDAE	12	DYSDERIDAE	6
ANYPHAENIDAE	6	ERESIDAE	43
ARANEIDAE PART 1, 2,3	214	PHILODROMIDAE	48
ARCHAEIDAE	20	PISAUROIDAE	58
ATYPIDAE	7	SICARIIDAE	24
BARYCHELIDAE	9	SPARASSIDAE	76
CAPONIIDAE	23	TETRAGNATHIDAE	47
CITHAERONIIDAE	7	THOMISIDAE 1-4	222
CTENIDAE	15	TROCHANTERIIDAE	17
CYATHOLIPIDAE	26	ULOBORIDAE	26
CYRTAUCHENIIDAE	37	27 families	1052 pages

This is a large and time-consuming project, and when eventually completed it will cover > 4000 pages.

ABSTRACTS OF THE FIRST EIGHT FAMILIES ARE PROVIDED ON THE NEXT THREE PAGES, INDICATING WHAT WE KNOW ABOUT EACH ONE.

THE AGELENIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.² & Lotz, L.N.⁴ 2020. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Agelenidae of South Africa*. 2020 version 1: 1-23.

The family Agelenidae occurs worldwide and is known from 82 genera and 1323 species (WSC 2020). Five genera represented by 10 species are presently known from South Africa, but only four are listed on the World Spider Catalog for South Africa. Most African genera of the family Agelenidae require revision, except *Mistaria*, which was revised by Kioko *et al.* (2019). Around 15 species from South Africa alone have been identified as possibly new or first records for the country. Of the 457 specimens presently housed in the National Collection of Arachnida only around 35% are identified to species level. Ten known species are listed as Least Concern. So far only one species, *Mistaria zuluana* (Roewer, 1955), is a South African endemic, and the three *Tegenaria* species are exotic species. The taxonomic status of the family are still poorly known with only 4 spp. listed on the WSC 2020 for South Africa. Fifteen new species is waiting to be described.

THE AMAUROBIIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.², Lotz, L.N.⁴ & Jocqué, R.⁵ 2020. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Amaurobiidae of South Africa*. 2020 version 1: 1-26.

The Amaurobiidae occurs worldwide and is known from 49 genera and 274 species. The family comprises several subfamilies, and one, Macrobuinae, is known from South Africa where it is represented by five genera and 16 species. All of them are South African endemics. The members of the genus *Chumma* were recently described. In a Ph.D study by Almeida-Silva (2013) on the rest of the Macrobuinae, seven new genera were proposed, but this work has never been published. Of the 603 amaurobiid specimens presently housed in the National Collection of Arachnida around 47% are identified to species level. Of the 16 known species, three species are listed as Least Concern, but for the majority, the status remains obscure and they are considered Data Deficient. Some more sampling is needed to collect both sexes and to determine the species' ranges. Only two species of amaurobiids are of special concern. The numbers of *Chumma inquieta* Jocqué, 2001 are declining due to ongoing loss of its coastal habitat to housing developments, and it qualifies as Endangered under criterion B. *Chumma striata* Jocqué & Alderweireldt, 2018 known from both sexes, is regarded as Rare due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (< 500 km²).

SUMMARY: Some genera are still poorly known; 7 new genera identified to be described.

THE AMMOXENIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.², & Lotz, L.N.⁴ 2020. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Ammoxenidae of South Africa*. 2020 version 1: 1-20.

The Ammoxenidae is a small family known only from Southern Africa and Australia and contains only four genera and 18 species (WSC 2020). From South Africa, two genera and nine species are known. Six *Ammoxenus* species are listed, but according to an unpublished study (T. Bird) at least 11 new species have been recognized.

In South Africa, the smaller *Rastellus* is known from only three species. The distribution and behaviour of most ammoxenid species are well recorded and the National Collection of Arachnida houses >1392 specimens. Seven of the species are listed as Least Concern, and two, *Ammoxenus daedalus* Dippenaar & Meyer, 1980 and *Rastellus florisbad* Platnick & Griffin, 1990, are Data Deficient. *Ammoxenus coccineus* Simon, 1893 and *Rastellus kariba* Platnick & Griffin, 1990 are not yet listed in the World Spider Catalog for South Africa. Eleven new species are waiting to be described.

THE ANAPIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.² & Lotz, L.N.⁴ 2020. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Anapidae of South Africa*. 2020 version 1: 1-12.

The Anapidae is a family known from 58 genera and 225 species. Three genera are known from South Africa, represented by four species. All three species are endemic to the country. The family Anapidae is not well studied in Africa and several new species are expected. It is rare in South Africa and only 77 specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida, of which 61 specimens are not identified. Based on the Conservation Assessment, only one species is of special concern. *Crozetulus scutatus* (Lawrence, 1964) has a small restricted distribution range, currently known from only one site and occurring within a protected area where there are no known threats. It is listed as Critically Rare. The other species, *C. rhodesiensis* Brignoli, 1981, recorded from other countries in southern Africa, is considered as Least Concern. The other two species are Data Deficient, although their status will change if the family is eventually revised.

SUMMARY: Only three genera and four species are known from South Africa, although several undescribed species have been collected.

THE ANYPHAENIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.², & Lotz, L.N.⁴ 2020. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Anyphaenidae of South Africa*. 2020 version 1: 1-6.

The family Anyphaenidae is represented by more than 56 genera and 565 species with a worldwide distribution. Only the genus *Amaurobioides*, represented by 12 species in the southern Hemisphere, is known from African. Only a single species has been described from South Africa, although at least one more species has been found.

Amaurobioides africana Hewitt, 1917 is a southern African endemic that has also been recorded from Namibia. In South Africa, the species is known from the rocky coastlines of East London in the Eastern Cape to several localities in the Western Cape and up to Port Nolloth in the Northern Cape. Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as being of Least Concern.

THE ARCHAEIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.² & Lotz, L.N.⁴ 2020. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Archaeidae of South Africa*. 2020 version 1: 1-20.

The family Archaeidae is known from five genera and 90 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). Only one genus *Afrarchaea* C. L. Koch & Berendt, 1854, represented by 14 species, are known from South Africa. Through a series of five papers all the species of the genus were described. They are rare spiders and not easily collected. Most of them are restricted endemics. *Afrarchaea neethlingi* Lotz, 2017 and *Afrarchaea entabeniensis* Lotz, 2003 are listed as Critically Rare and *Afrarchaea cornuta* (Lotz, 2003) and *Afrarchaea woodae* Lotz, 2006 are Vulnerable, *Afrarchaea cornuta* (Lotz, 2003) and *Afrarchaea woodae* Lotz, 2006 is Endangered, *Afrarchaea neethlingi* Lotz, 2017 is Rare. The status of six species remains obscure and they are listed as Data Deficient. Only two species *Afrarchaea bergae* Lotz, 1996 and *Afrarchaea godfreyi* Hewitt, 1919 have a wide distribution and is of Least Concern.

THE ARANEIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.², Lotz, L.N.⁴ & Webb, P.⁵ 2020. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Araneidae of South Africa* 2020 version 1: part 1 A-C (70 pp.); part 2 D-N (63 pp.); part 3 N-U, references (64 pp.).

The family Araneidae has a worldwide distribution, with a rich diversity of 174 genera and 3128 species. With the large number of specimens sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), several genera have been identified as possible new records for South Africa. In this guide we discuss 47 genera represented by 105 species that are all listed on the South African National Species List, but 16 of these genera represented by 36 species are not listed on the World Spider Catalog for South Africa yet. Only 21 of the species are South African endemics. Of the 105 species, 93 (88%) have a wide distribution and are listed as Least Concern and nine are Data Deficient. Only three species are of special concern: *Caerostris tinamaze* Gregorič, 2015 being Vulnerable under the B criterion, and the two bolas spiders, *Cladomelea akermani* Hewitt, 1923 and *Cladomelea debeeri* Roff & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2004, are listed as Endangered. There are numerous new species that still need to be described and both sexes are known for only 66 species. It will therefore take time before the exact status of the Araneidae will be known.

THE ATYPIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S.^{1,2}, Haddad, C.R.³, Foord, S.H.² & Lotz, L.N.⁴ 2020. *South African National Survey of Arachnida Photo Identification Guide: The Atypidae of South Africa*. 2020 version 1: 1-7.

The family Atypidae is known from five genera and 90 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). Only one genus, *Calommata* Lucas, 1837, represented by 13 species, is known from Africa (six species), of which two are known from South Africa. They are very rare spiders and both of them are restricted endemics. *Calommata meridionalis* Fourie, Haddad & Jocqué, 2011 is listed as Near Threatened under the B criterion, and *C. transvaalica* Hewitt, 1916 is Vulnerable under the B criterion.

THE NATIONAL COLLECTION OF ARACHNIDA DATABASE IS MIGRATING TO SPECIFY

The National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) database has come a long way. In 1994, the African Arachnida Database (AFRAD) was developed in conjunction with the Royal Museum for Central Africa, Tervuren, Belgium. As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) in 2006 to 2007, a MySQL database known as the Arachnida database was developed at the Agricultural Research Council (ARC). This database incorporated the existing AFRAD database, and two new modules were added: 1) the National Collection module, which holds the digitized records of all the specimens held in the NCA; and 2) the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) module, which holds the digitized records of all the published taxonomic and ecological articles on South African arachnid species. During 2016, the Arachnida database as a whole was migrated to a SQL database by the ARC-Information Systems Unit.

In fulfilment of an agreement reached and facilitated by the Natural Science Collections Facility (NSCF) between the ARC and South African National Biodiversity Institute (SANBI), all biosystematics collections are now in the process of being integrated into the Specify database platform. The proposed timeline to conclusion for this is June 2020 to March 2021.

The NSCF was established as part of the Department of Science & Innovation's (DSI) Research Infrastructure Roadmap and is coordinated by SANBI. The NSCF is a network of South African institutions that hold natural science collections, and is dedicated to the preservation, upgrade and promotion of research on natural science collections and associated data, to enable a sustainable, enriched life on Earth. The ARC has been a proud participating institution since its inception.

Specify has supported collections of all biological disciplines with software for over 30 years. Today, Specify research data management systems are implemented in 450+ collections in 38 countries.

Specify manages species and specimen data for computerizing biodiversity research collections, tracking collection specimen transactions, linking images to specimen records and publishing catalog data to the Internet. Specify supports data from specimens, taxonomic classifications, field notebooks, DNA sequence runs, literature references, as well as from other primary sources. It also manages the information associated with repository agreements, accessions, conservation treatments, collection object containers, images, and document attachments. Data fields in Specify's form windows can be selected, organized, re-named, and re-sized to suit your preferences. Specify's "tree" data windows for taxonomy, geography and storage location provide intuitive access to hierarchical data for editing, drag-and-drop synonymization, and for discovering linked collection objects. Retrieving data is facilitated by Specify's full-text "Simple Search", which provides access to every data table and field. Records resulting from searches and queries may be exported to a Microsoft Excel format file, printed as labels or reports, or saved in a Specify 'Record Set'.

Specify also provides embedded georeferencing with the Tulane University's 'GEOLocate' service, custom printed label and report design, and specimen data exporting.

During the migration process, we would still have access to all existing data in the Arachnida database up to the end of May 2020. However, all new data and edits on existing data will be captured in a Microsoft Excel file, which will only be incorporated to the Specify database on completion of the migration.

Contact: Petro Marais maraisp@arc.agric.za

Information on specimens housed in the collection.

FEEDBACK ON A STUDENT PROJECT

Jurie Theron completed his MSc at the University of Stellenbosch (See SANSА Newsletter 2016, 29: 9). With this research he made an important contribution to sampling spiders in the Cape Floristic Region (CFR), a biodiversity hotspot. He published two articles on his results, of which we provide the abstracts here. All the spiders collected (272 samples) are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida.

ABANDONED FIELDS AND HIGH PLANT DIVERSITY SUPPORT HIGH SPIDER DIVERSITY WITHIN AN AGRICULTURAL MOSAIC IN A BIODIVERSITY HOTSPOT

K. Jurie Theron, Rene Gaigher, James S. Pryke & Michael J. Samways

Biodiversity and Conservation

<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-020-02048-9>

Abstract Protected areas alone cannot conserve all biodiversity; we must also conserve biodiversity within production landscapes. Little is known about spider diversity in the Cape Floristic Region (CFR) biodiversity hotspot and factors driving spider diversity in transformed landscapes. Here, we assess spatial patterns of spiders in different transformed biotopes bordering remnant fynbos natural vegetation patches, determine direction of associated edge effects, and identify environmental factors influencing spider local distribution. Spiders were sampled along replicated transects running from remnant patches into three different transformed biotopes: old-fields (abandoned farmland), vineyards, and alien tree plantations. Spider Shannon diversity within old-fields and plantations did not differ from remnant patches, which had the highest diversity, whereas vineyards had the lowest. Overall, spider diversity was consistently high around habitat boundaries, regardless of land use type. Vineyards showed sharp declines in spider diversity along the remnant vineyard transect, compared to other transects. Spider assemblages within vineyards was significantly different compared to remnant patches and old-fields, whereas other land-uses showed greater similarity. Plant species richness within the transformed biotope core increased overall spider diversity, benefiting plant-dwelling assemblages, but negatively influencing ground-dwelling assemblages. Herbaceous plant cover was driving assemblages within vineyards, whereas Restionaceae plant cover drove assemblages within old fields. Furthermore, amount of natural vegetation in the landscape influenced spider assemblages within transformed biotopes. Our results show that old-fields have great potential to increase structural and functional connectivity within agricultural mosaics, and their rehabilitation is recommended. Furthermore, increasing plant diversity throughout the transformed landscape can soften the landscape and benefit spider diversity.

Sampling sites: Natural vegetation spared in the Bottelary Conservancy, Bottelary Hills, Brackenell, South Africa.

Abandoned vineyard becoming an old field, increasing functional connectivity within the landscape.

HIGH QUALITY REMNANT PATCHES IN A COMPLEX AGRICULTURAL LANDSCAPE SUSTAIN HIGH SPIDER DIVERSITY

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Biological Conservation 243: 108480 (2020).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108480>

Abstract. Remnant vegetation in agricultural landscapes can play a significant role in supporting farmland biodiversity, especially agriculturally important arthropods such as spiders. Little is known about spider composition in native vegetation remnant patches, or which environmental parameters influence within-patch diversity. Furthermore, data on spider diversity is limited in the Greater Cape Floristic Region (GCFR), a global botanical hotspot of great conservation value. Here we sampled spiders in 12 remnant natural fynbos (sclerophyllous) patches in a fragmented agricultural landscape. Multiple environmental variables were measured at each site (within patch variables and landscape variables), to determine their influence on spider genus richness and assemblage structure. We also did this for ground- and plant-dwelling genera, as well as for their assemblages separately. Overall, natural vegetation remnants supported high spider diversity, even rare and range restricted species. Both patch- and landscape- scale variables influenced spider diversity and assemblage structure. Remnant patch size influenced the assemblage structure of all guilds, and positively influenced overall spider diversity.

Peter Webb

Phrynarachne melloleitai (Thomisidae), one of the species sampled

Similarly, the amount of remnant vegetation in the landscape influenced the assemblage structure of most guilds, as well as positively influencing overall spider diversity, across multiple spatial scales. Additional important variables were rockiness, alien invasive tree species richness and topographic complexity. We show that spider diversity is maintained by remnants of good quality natural vegetation, but also influenced by the complexity of the landscape. Preservation of remnant vegetation patches, regardless of size, through out the privately-owned farm conservancy landscape maintains spider diversity, and so private land conservation should be promoted.

SUCCULENT KAROO/DESERT PROJECT

The Succulent Karoo (SKB) and Desert (DB) biomes are found in the arid western part of South Africa, predominantly in the Western and Northern Cape provinces, with the former being a recognized global biodiversity hotspot (Myers *et al.* 2000). Despite their unique climate, landscapes and vegetation, these biomes remain very poorly sampled for most arachnids, excluding scorpions, which have been well sampled. Although a sizable number of spider species have been recorded in these biomes, particularly the SKB, endemism here is high (Foord *et al.* 2020). The distribution of the species here generally remains poorly known.

This problem is exacerbated by 1) the lack of sampling during recent decades in the two biomes (e.g. Janion-Scheepers *et al.* 2016), which has left large areas unsampled and their fauna unknown; 2) some ambiguity regarding the type localities and distribution of species described by Purcell (1908) and Simon (1910) in western South Africa (Haddad & Marusik 2019); and 3) the lack of modern revisions or redescriptions of many of the species described from this part of South Africa. Considering the shortage of illustrations in the descriptions of Purcell and Simon, identification of the species recorded here has been very problematic and uncertain.

Further, no intensive ecological surveys on spiders have been carried out in these two biomes to date, although spiders were included in studies on invertebrate bioindicators and ecological responses to restored diamond mining sites (Lyons 2009; Steed *et al.* 2018). During recent years, some collecting was undertaken by staff of the ARC as part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) and as part of targeted collecting for the taxonomic projects of Zingisile Mbo (Ph.D) and Ruan Booysen (M.Sc) at the University of the Free State.

During 2020, Charles Haddad submitted a successful proposal to study patterns of spider biodiversity in the DB and SKB as part of the Foundational Biodiversity Information Programme (FBIP). The project will consist of five components:

- 1) A desktop study will be undertaken to determine the existing spider species recorded from the DB and SKB in the published literature and SANSa database.
- 2) Field surveys will be conducted in five subcoastal degree-squares in western South Africa, from the Richtersveld National Park in the north (DB, 28 degrees S), through four SKB sites to the Tankwa Karoo National Park in the south (32 degrees S). A standardized protocol will be used to collect in four biotopes per degree-square (e.g. open plain, riparian vegetation, eastern and western slopes of a hill), in both summer and winter, to generate comparable datasets to determine local species richness, as well as species turnover between sites. Due to the structure of the biotopes (restricting the use of sweep-netting and litter sifting) and time restrictions (preventing the use of pitfall sampling), sampling will be conducted entirely using foliage beating and hand collecting for fixed time intervals.
- 3) Specimens collected during the field surveys will be preserved in ~99% ethanol for DNA barcoding. We plan to collect enough material to be able to submit one plate of 95 specimens from each degree-square per each sampling trip for DNA barcoding (COI gene). This will result in a total of 950 specimens being submitted for barcoding. Ideally, we would like to include at least one male and female of each morphospecies for sequencing, and in genera with multiple species we could include multiple specimens, to try and successfully match males and females of individual species. The sequences and collecting data will be loaded to the existing SPIZA (Spiders of South Africa) project on BOLD.
- 4) Following tissue removal for DNA barcoding, specimens will be deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida in Pretoria (NCA) for use in taxonomic studies. Specimens of genera currently under study by participants in the project will be retained for immediate inclusion in their taxonomic projects. Specimen records will be provided to the co-ordinators of FBIP as one of the outcomes of the project.
- 5) Once all material has been identified and deposited in the NCA, the data will be added to the lists of the arachnids of the two biomes generated as part of the desktop study, and a review paper on the biodiversity of the non-acarine arachnids of the SKB and DB submitted for publication.

We hope that through this study to generate a considerable number of new distribution records of spiders in the DB and SKB, including three national parks (Richtersveld, Namaqua and Tankwa Karoo), and to showcase the biodiversity and endemism of the species here. Further, the latitudinal gradient will enable us to determine whether climatic and vegetative gradients are similarly reflected through changes in the spider diversity. The material generated will also contribute to taxonomic studies, particularly enabling matching of sexes or discovery of undescribed sexes, and DNA barcoding projects to facilitate identification of spiders in the future.

The infamous wildflower season of Namaqualand is a major tourist attraction and highlights the biodiversity of Succulent Karoo Biome (Photos: Ina Erasmus).

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THERON, K.J., GAIGHER, R., PRYKE, J.S. & SAMWAYS, M.J. 2020. Abandoned fields and high plant diversity support high spider diversity within an agricultural mosaic in a biodiversity hotspot. *Biodiversity and Conservation*.29:3757–3782 [https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-020-02048-9\(0123456789\(\).-volV\)\(0123456789\(\).-volV\)](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10531-020-02048-9(0123456789().-volV)(0123456789().-volV))

THERON, K.J., GAIGHER, R., PRYKE, J.S. & SAMWAYS, M.J. 2020. High quality remnant patches in a complex agricultural landscape sustain high spider diversity. *Biological Conservation* 243:108480. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2020.108480>

PLEASE TAKE NOTE

John Luyt sent us photographs of a Filistatidae species that they found in their house at Hoedspruit. Some filistatid spiders can become invasive, based on reports received from Namibia.

Anka Eichhoff provided a photo of this tree in Namibia that is covered with silk.

Please send us a message if you find them in or around houses or other anthropogenic structures.

MORE ON *CLADOMELEA LONGIPES* (ARANEAE: ARANEIDAE)

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Abstract: The bolas spider *Cladomelea longipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) has a wide distribution in Africa, and is known from Cameroon, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Zimbabwe and South Africa. In this paper we report on new information on their mating, feeding and egg cocoon construction.

Key words: Spider, mating, egg cocoon, feeding, Africa

In a recent publication by Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019), the bolas spider, *Cladomelea longipes* (O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1877) was reported from South Africa for the first time. *Cladomelea longipes* differs from its congeners in the colour of the body and shape of the abdomen and copulatory organs.

The carapace is greyish-pink and covered in dense setae, giving it a woolly appearance. The carapace is broad, rounded posteriorly, and narrowed anteriorly. The ocular tubercle is high and bears a row of three strong erect spines medially. The abdomen is triangular, dorsally pink, and infused with a grey guanophore and silky hair, giving it a woolly appearance. Two large, yellow, round tubercles are present on the antero-lateral corners of the abdomen, and four smaller white round tubercles are arranged in rows in between (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Foord (2019)).

I recently received some excellent photographs of *C. longipes* from Tinus Odendaal of a female he observed over a period of several weeks in Cameroon (Fig. 1). He was able to capture some of their interesting behavior, including using their bolas to catch moths, on camera.

Figure 1. *Cladomelea longipes* female on a leaf.

However, it was only when studying the photographs that we observed the very tiny black male in the vicinity of the female (Fig. 2a, b). The male, which is about 10x smaller than the female, is still undescribed. Of the species of *Cladomelea*, only the male of *C. akermani* Hewitt, 1923 is known, which was described by Leroy *et al.* (1998). The two males seem to be similar in shape and size. In *C. longipes*, the male's abdomen is decorated with a pale spot near the posterior end.

Figure 2. (a) *Cladomelea longipes* female, and to the top left the very small male; (b) Close-up of the very small undescribed male.

The mating process of *Cladomelea* spp. has never been recorded. A very interesting observation was made when the small male was observed sitting on the epigyne of the female on some of the photographs. The white spot on the abdomen of the male was clearly visible, indicating that he sits with his venter pressed against her epigyne. What is more interesting is that he stayed there for a few days, even while she was feeding (Fig. 3a, b).

Figure 3. (a, b) *Cladomelea longipes* female, ventral view, showing the tiny male sitting on her epigyne while she is still feeding.

Figure 4. (a) *Cladomelea longipes* female hanging from trapezium web, with bolas with two sticky droplets; (b) *Cladomelea longipes* female, swinging her leg with the bolas; (c) *Cladomelea longipes* female with the moth she has captured (left), while another moth landing on them (right).

The general behaviour of making the bolas (Fig. 4a) and swinging it around (Fig. 4b) was very similar to that of *C. akermani*. During the observation period, only moths were caught. It is still unknown whether *Cladomelea* spp. also release false pheromones to attract male moths. On one image (Fig. 4c) the female was feeding on a moth while another moth landed on them, having possibly been attracted by pheromones of the captured moth or false pheromone of the spider.

EGG COCOONS: The egg cocoon constructed by *C. longipes* differs from that of other known *Cladomelea* species. The female eventually constructed four egg sacs that were observed suspended 0.5 to 1.9 metres above the ground (Figs 5a, b).

Figure 5. (a,b) *Cladomelea longipes* female constructing egg cocoons that hang from reinforced silk threads.

The incubation period is about 40 days. The spiderlings (>100) emerged and stay together for up to 36 hours after hatching (Fig. 6a,b). During breezier days they left the hatching site quicker. Ballooning was observed when few lift off with the breeze, attached to a length of silk.

Figure 6. (a,b). *Cladomelea longipes* egg cocoons with spiderlings.

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NOTES ON THE ORB-WEB SPIDER *ARANEUS APRICUS* (KARSCH, 1884) IN SOUTH AFRICA (ARANEAE: ARANEIDAE)

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Abstract: Data on the species diversity of *Araneus* (Araneidae) in South Africa is limited and outdated. A large number of Araneidae species were sampled during the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA). *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884), a species known from São Tomé, Yemen, Seychelles and Senegal, is also now recorded from South Africa. The presence of *A. apricus* in South Africa is discussed, with notes on their morphology based on live photographs, behaviour and distribution.

Key words: spider, web building, distribution, medical importance. South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) large numbers of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). This includes many Araneidae specimens. Data on the current *Araneus* species diversity in South Africa is limited and outdated. For the first time, the green pea orb-web spider, *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884), an African endemic species, was identified from South Africa. The species is known from the type locality, São Tomé, and has also been sampled in Yemen, Seychelles and Senegal (World Spider Catalog 2020).

The objective of this study is to discuss the behaviour, distribution and conservation status of *A. apricus* in South Africa, with notes on their morphology based on photographs of live specimens.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The specimens examined are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA). As part of SANSA requests were made for photographs for the SANSA Virtual Museum and several were received (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012).

TAXONOMY

Araneus apricus (Karsch, 1884)

Epeira aprica Karsch, 1884: 67, fig. 8 (Df).

Araneus apricus Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2014.

Diagnostic characters: Size: TL females 8–7 mm, males slightly smaller and with darker markings. *Araneus apricus* can be easily recognised by their distinct body shape and green abdomen. Carapace shiny, blackish brown (Figs 1-3); cephalic region raised, bearing scattered white setae (Fig. 5). Eyes in two rows; lateral eyes situated close together near carapace edge; anterior median eyes largest, well separated; posterior median eyes closer together (Fig. 2). Sternum brown, heart-shaped, bearing scattered long white setae (Fig. 4). Abdomen round, partly overlapping the carapace; shoulder humps not distinct; integument bearing short white setae (Fig. 5); dark

patch present on anterior edge, sometimes stretching on both sides to half abdomen length; area around patch sometimes with yellow tint (Fig. 5); abdomen pale brown ventrally, with yellow spots on both sides of epigynum (Fig. 4). Legs paler than carapace, varying from brown with distinct bands on femora and tibiae (Figs 2-4) to brown without bands (Fig. 5). Epigyne with long scape (Fig. 8). Male unknown.

Behaviour: They build their orb-webs at night (Fig. 7) and remove them in the early morning. They spend the day in a retreat composed of a cluster of leaves pulled together with silk threads (Fig. 6). The cryptic colouration of the abdomen helps to camouflage them. Field observations showed that the species is much more abundant in the summer months. They appear to be largely restricted to the shrub and tree layer, between 1.5 and 2 m above ground level.

Medical importance: This species is one of the few araneids for which a case study on their bite symptoms exists (Haddad 2002). The bite was not especially painful, local swelling and red dermal colouration around the bite site developed, with the thumb and forefinger area becoming numb. Within the first hour sharp pain developed in the bicep, armpit, shoulder, lateral chest and pectoral muscles, after which discomfort levels decreased. Lymph glands in the armpit also started to swell during this time. Intense pain began developing in the thumb and index finger an hour after envenomation, and continued during the subsequent hours. Local swelling around the bite site gradually increased to an area approximately 2.5 cm in diameter, which was bright red in colour and extremely itchy. Swelling of the hand and armpit glands receded within 8 hours of the bite. A small scar formed at the site of the bite marks, which healed after 16 days (without any treatment), and no tissue necrosis occurred.

Habitat: They have been sampled from several of the floral biomes in South Africa, such as the Savanna (Foord *et al.* 2011), Grassland (Haddad *et al.* 2013), as well as the Fynbos, Forest and Nama Karoo biomes. The species were also found in agroecosystems such as avocado, citrus and macadamia orchards and tomato fields (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2013).

Figure 1–9. *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884) females from South Africa. (1) Dorsal view; (2) Anterior view, showing eye pattern and band on abdomen; (3) Dorsolateral view, showing the carapace shape; (4) Ventral view; (5) Dorsal view, showing colour variation; (6) Female in retreat; (7) Female in orb-web; (8) Epigyne, ventral view; (9) Map showing the known distribution of *Araneus apricus* (Karsch, 1884) in South Africa. Photos Peter Webb, except 8, A. Dippenaar-Schoeman.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park (-33.343, 25.739), leg. L. Wiese, 1 f (NCA 2011/1289); Baviaanskloof Nature Reserve (Ferndale Farm, Keurkloof) (-33.656, 24.541), leg. M. le Roux, 1f (NCA 2009/3133); Coffee Bay (-31.981, 29.152), leg. C. Haddad & R. Lyle, beating, 1f (NCA 2007/393). **Gauteng:** Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.80, 28.77), leg. R. Lyle, 2f (NCA 2005/1391); Same locality, leg. A. Leroy, 2f (NCA 2005/1391); Pretoria (-25.74, 28.19), leg. S. Nesar, 1f (NCA 91/164); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36), leg. M. Stiller, 13.xi.1980, 1f (NCA 92/244); Wonderboom Nature Reserve (-25.69, 28.19), leg. A. Dippenaar, 1.ii.1981, 1f (NCA 81/647). **KwaZulu-Natal:** iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Mkuze Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25), leg. S. Lovell, 1f (NCA 2004/156); iSimangaliso Wetland Park, Kosi Bay Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.87), leg. P. Reavell, 6.x.1977, 1imm. f (NCA 78/177); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24), leg. C. Haddad, 1f (NCA 2011/1289); Pongola, Farm Vergeval (-27.35, 31.61), leg. A. Dippenaar, 2.vi.1967, 1imm. f (NCA 77/1016); Tembe Elephant Park (-

26.94, 32.47), leg. C. Haddad, 1f (NCA 2008/1598); Umgeni Valley Nature Reserve (-29.47, 30.20), leg. J. Leroy, 1f (NCA 2009/5393). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit (-24.34, 30.93), leg. B. Grobbelaar, 18.i.1991, 1f (NCA 91/89); Kruger National Park, Pafuri (-22.93, 31.06), leg. J. Braack, 18.iii.1974, 1f (NCA 91/1660); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve, Farm Malta (-24.162, 30.254), leg. P. Webb, 3.ii.2015, 5f (NCA 2015/3500); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45), leg. R. Lyle & R. Fourie, 1f (NCA 2008/484); Letaba (-23.82, 30.16), leg. C.J. Cilliers, 12.xii.1979, 1f (NCA 81/556); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52, 28.70), leg. A. Leroy, 4.iv.1980, 3f (NCA 81/146); Nylstroom/ Modimolle (-24.69, 28.40), leg. A. Honiball, sweeping, 1f (NCA 2008/791); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67), leg. G. Ferreira, 7.iii.1976, 1f (NCA 78/473); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.90, 29.47), leg. T. Khoza & M. Modiba, sweeping, 1f (NCA 2008/2136); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63), leg. M. Filmer, 3.iv.1986, 1f (NCA 87/138); Sandringham Nature Reserve (-24.58, 31.10), leg. N. Dippenaar, 7.iv.1974, 1f (NCA 76/835); Soutpansberg, Farm Little Leigh (-

22.95, 29.87), leg. N. Hahn, 1f (NCA 2009/1996). **Mpumalanga:** Badplaas (-25.95, 30.56), leg. J. van As, 1m (NCA 2005/337); Brondal (-25.35, 30.84), leg. M van den Berg, 7.iv.1998, avocado, 1f (NCA 98/1006); Burgers Hall (-25.08, 31.08), leg. M. van den Berg, citrus, 2f (NCA 2009/649); Loskop Dam Nature Reserve (-25.46, 29.23), leg. A. Dippenaar, 6.iv.1974, 1f (NCA 76/1816); Lowveld National Botanical Gardens (-25.47, 31.00), leg. A. Leroy, 1f (NCA 2008/2675); Nelspruit (-25.47, 30.96), leg. M van den Berg, fogging macadamia trees, 1f (NCA 98/789). **Northern Cape:** Hopetown, Farm Suffolk (-29.58, 24.24), leg. R. Lyle & R. Fourie, 1f (NCA 2010/771); Rooipoort Nature Reserve, leg. R. Lyle & P. Lyle, 22.iii.2013, 1f (NCA 2015/4242). **North West:** Borakalalo Game Reserve (-25.14, 27.82), leg. M. Filmer, 26.iii.1989, 1f (NCA 89/912); Hartbeespoortdam (-25.73, 27.85), leg. A. Capener, 10.iii.1966, 1imm. f (NCA 77/1019); Kroondal (-25.75, 27.32), leg. M. Filmer, 15.iii.1978, 1f (NCA 87/472); Magaliesburg (-25.99, 27.54), leg. M. Filmer, 3.iii.1987, 1m (NCA 87/692); Rustenburg Nature Reserve (-25.72, 27.18), leg. M. Stiller, 30.iv.1981, 1f (NCA 84/288). **Western Cape:** De Hoop Nature Reserve (-34.45, 20.44), leg. C. Haddad, 1f (NCA 2007/3855); Jonkershoek Nature Reserve (-33.98, 18.98), leg. E. Pietersen, 1f (NCA 2010/3293); Outeniqua Nature Reserve (-33.92, 22.43), leg. D. Damon, 1f (NCA 2010/2402).

Global distribution: An African endemic species that was described from São Tomé and has been collected from four African countries (São Tomé, Yemen [mainland Socotra], Seychelles and South Africa). This species is possibly undercollected and suspected to occur in more countries in-between. In South Africa it is fairly common and has been collected from eight provinces (Fig. 9).

Conservation status: The species receives protection in several protected areas such as: Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2009), Roodeplaat Dam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 1989), Luvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.* 2008), Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad *et al.* 2006), Tembe Elephant Park (Haddad *et al.* 2009), Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord *et al.* 2016) and De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009). Due to the species' wide range, and the absence of threats to its survival, it is listed according to the IUCN criteria as Least Concern.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study was made possible through financial support from the Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the National Research Foundation of South Africa. Authors want to thank Peter Webb for sharing his photographs.

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NEW LOCALITY DATA FOR THE ORB-WEB SPIDER *ARANEUS COCCINELLA* POCOCK, 1898 FROM SOUTH AFRICA (ARANEAE: ARANEIDAE)

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Abstract: *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898 is a South African endemic described from a female collected in Estcourt in KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa. Prior to this paper, the species was only known from the type specimen. It is a rare spider and is now known from a few localities in Gauteng, KwaZulu-Natal and Limpopo in South Africa. The aim of this paper is to add notes on the morphology of *A. coccinella* based on images of living spiders, and provide information on its behaviour and distribution.

Key words: biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA)

INTRODUCTION

Data on *Araneus* species diversity in South Africa is limited and outdated. According to the World Spider Catalog (2020), 13 *Araneus* species are known from South Africa, all of which were described between 1898 and 1950. In a recent publication by Nentwig *et al.* (2020), five of these species were listed as *nomina dubia*. The only recent paper on South African *Araneus* was the transfer of *Larinia vara* Kauri, 1950 to *Araneus* (Marusik 2017).

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), large numbers of arachnid specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015). The identification of the araneids is a problem, as most of the genera have not been revised. As part of SANSA, a Virtual Museum database was developed to provide access to the photographs submitted by the public for identification (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2012). For the first time, images of living specimens of the coccinella spider, *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898, were available. *Araneus coccinella* is a South African endemic that was described from Estcourt in KwaZulu-Natal, and could be positively identified based on Pocock's (1898) description.

The aim of this paper is to add notes on the morphology of *A. coccinella* based on images of living spiders, their behaviour and distribution.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Araneus coccinella spiders were sampled during SANSA and the voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA).

TAXONOMY

Araneus coccinella Pocock, 1898

Araneus coccinella Pocock, 1898: 211, pl. 8, fig. 6 (Df).

Type: Holotype female from South Africa, KwaZulu-Natal, Estcourt (-29.01, 29.87), deposited in British Museum of Natural History (not examined).

Diagnostic characters: Female: Size: total length 6 mm. *Araneus coccinella* can easily be recognised by their body shape and spotted abdomen (Fig. 1). Carapace varies from cream with dark patches in thoracic region in younger specimens (Fig. 2) to black in older females (Fig. 4); cephalic region slightly elevated, bearing numerous white setae; in older specimens the white hairs are restricted to the cephalic region; carapace slightly longer than wide (Fig. 1). Female palp yellow-orange. Eyes in two rows; anterior eye row recurved; posterior eye row almost straight (viewed from above); median eyes widely separated from lateral eyes; eyes small, all same size. Sternum dark, heart-shaped. Legs short, with coxae and trochanters black, remaining leg segments orange-yellow, with black bands on distal ends of all of the metatarsi and tarsi. Abdomen oval, longer than wide; anterior portion rounded, posterior rounded and projecting slightly beyond the spinnerets; orange-yellow above, decorated with eight black oval spots, arranged in two parallel lines (Figs 1-2); in some specimens the anterior spots merge (Fig. 4). Venter entirely black (Fig. 3). Epigynum: with short triangular scape (Figs 5a-b), deeply excavated above, ending posteriorly in a rounded apex. Male unknown.

Figure 1. *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898 female from Soutpansberg, dorsal view (Photo: Peter Webb).

Figures 2-4. *Araneus coccinella* Pocock, 1898. (2) Female from Irene, dorsal view; (3) Female from Irene, lateral view; (4) Female from Wakefield Farm, dorsal view, showing the variation in abdominal markings (Photos: P. Webb).

Figures 5-6. (5) Ventral epigyne of *Araneus coccinella* from Soutpansberg (Photo: A. Dippenaar-Schoeman); (6) Original line drawing of female epigyne by Pocock (1898).

Habitat: The species was sampled with a sweepnet from grassland. In Irene, Gauteng, a small grassland patch was regularly sampled over a period of ten years. Specimens of *A. coccinella* were regularly found during the summer months (November to February) and were sampled in 2011, 2014-2016 and 2019. In the Limpopo Province, it was sampled during altitudinal transect surveys in the Western Soutpansberg.

Global distribution: South Africa. New records: South Africa (Gauteng,

Figure 7. Records of *Araneus coccinella* in South Africa.

Material examined: SOUTH AFRICA: Gauteng: Irene veld (opposite Gem Village) (-25.87, 28.23), leg. P. Webb, 2.xi.2011, 1f (NCA 2011/385); Same locality, 4.ii.2014, leg. P. Webb, 1f (NCA 2015/3314); Same locality, 20.xii.2015, leg. P. Webb, 1f (NCA 2020/551); Same locality, 10.1.2016, leg. P. Webb, 1f (NCA 2020/552). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Wakefield Farm, near Howick (-29.50, 29.89), 23.xi.2015, leg. P. Webb, 1f (NCA 2020/553).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This study was made possible by the financial support from Agricultural Research Council (ARC) and the National Research Foundation of South Africa.

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NOTES ON THE VELVET SPIDER *GANDANAMENO FUMOSA* (C. L. KOCH, 1837) FROM SOUTHERN AFRICA (ARANEAE: ERESIDAE)

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Abstract: The large velvet spiders of the African genus *Gandanameno* Lehtinen, 1967 are known from five species. One of the species, the tree velvet spider *Gandanameno fumosa* (C.L. Koch, 1837) is known from South Africa and now also from Namibia. The species was observed over a period of 18 months. This paper reports on their web building and feeding behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Key words: behaviour, predation, taxonomy, distribution, conservation

INTRODUCTION

The Eresidae in southern Africa is represented by five genera (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2020). Three genera, *Paradonea* Lawrence, 1968 (Miller *et al.* 2012), *Seothyra* Purcell, 1903 (Dippenaar-Schoeman 1991) and *Stegodyphus* Simon, 1873 (Kraus & Kraus 1988) have been revised and information is available on their distribution and lifestyle. However, the genera *Dresserus* Simon, 1876 and *Gandanameno* Lehtinen, 1967 are less known and in need of revisions.

The velvet spiders *Gandanameno* and *Dresserus* resemble each other in general appearance and shape. They both share a peculiar modification of the median spinnerets. However, they differ in the cribellum of *Dresserus* being 4-partite, having a secondary septum in both plates, compared to the 2-partite of *Gandanameno*. In the males, *Dresserus* can be distinguished by having two horn-like tubercles on the antero-lateral border of the carapace.

It is frequently difficult to distinguish between *Dresserus* and *Gandanameno* species only from photographs. Based on the combination of genetic, morphometric, and spinulation data, Miller *et al.* (2012) saw no evidence that the characters traditionally used to discriminate *Gandanameno* species are valid. They speculated that ontogenetic factors may be responsible for the morphological variation observed in species of this genus. However, they decided that the synonymy of all *Gandanameno* species would be premature, particularly in light of the phylogeographic signal suggested by the molecular data.

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) large numbers of specimens were sampled (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2015, 2020), including several eresid genera such as *Gandanameno*. The genus *Gandanameno* is currently known from five species. One has been reported from Malawi, but the other four all originate from southern Africa (World Spider Catalog 2020). Of these, three species were described from South Africa and one from Namibia.

During SANSa, several species of *Gandanameno* were identified, including the tree velvet spider *Gandanameno fumosa* (C.L. Koch, 1837). The female of *G. fumosa* was described by as *Eresus fumosus*, with the type locality only given as "Africa" (C.L. Koch 1837). Tucker (1920) described the male

for the first time, based on a specimen from Naauwpoort, near Hanover in the Northern Cape. *Gandanameno fumosa* was assessed for the IUCN Red List (Foord *et al.* 2020).

The first author (AE) collected a male and female eresid in Namibia and sent it to the second author (ASD) for identification. The specimens were identified as *G. fumosa*. This represents the first confirmed record of this species from Namibia. Specimens were observed over a period of 18 months in Namibia, and in this paper we provide information on the behaviour, distribution and conservation status of *G. fumosa* in southern Africa.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study area: The first author observed *Gandanameno* activity on the farms Vergenoeg (21°11.53'S, 18°18.34'E) and Otjitambi in the Outjo district of Namibia over a period of 18 months. The spider activity was documented and specimens were photographed.

Voucher specimens: A male and female from Namibia have been deposited as voucher specimens in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA 2020/554) at the Agricultural Research Council in Pretoria. Specimens sampled during the SANSa surveys are also housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA).

Photographs: All the photographs were taken by the first author.

RESULTS

Species morphology: *Gandanameno fumosa* is a large spider with a velvety appearance. It is very closely allied to *E. echinatus* (Purcell, 1908), a species known from Namibia, the only differences being the spinous integument of the sternum and parts of the legs. In *E. fumosus*, the sternum is thickly covered with minute sharp spinules distributed between the setae, the coxae of the two anterior legs, and the third coxa are also more densely spinulose. The patellae of the two anterior pairs of legs are covered in dense but very short spinules on the anterior side. It shares with *G. purcelli* (Tucker, 1920) the white spotted abdomen, but differs by the more densely spinulose areas.

Description: Female (Figs 1 & 3): body size: 23–25 mm. Carapace rectangular; dark-brown, almost black, slightly darker in cephalic region; cephalic region strongly raised, densely clothed with setae; fovea circular; eyes eight, median eyes close together, with lateral eyes wide apart and posterior lateral eyes usually positioned far back on the carapace. Abdomen oval and densely clothed with setae; dark grey with short setae that form small white spots and faint chevron markings; white setae form white rings around dorsal sigilla; cribellum 2-partite. Legs same colour as carapace; stout and thickly clothed with setae; tarsi and metatarsi usually united by almost rigid joints; coxae and femora I and II densely spinulose (Fig. 6). Sternum thickly covered with minute, sharp spinules. Epigyne with copulatory openings that are broadly separated by hirsute cuticle (Fig. 5).

Male (Figs 2 & 3): smaller in size, 9-10 mm. Carapace dark-brown, almost black; slightly arched posterior to fovea, thus leaving a more level, fan-shaped area on each side from fovea to border; surface finely granular and covered in white setae; thoracic portion broader than cephalic region, also covered in white setae. Abdomen infuscated testaceous, slightly darker on under surface and sparsely covered with short whitish hairs and longer darker ones; dorsal sigilla white-ringed, and posterior to sigilla are 4-5 light oblique markings sloping down from central line. Sternum dark brown. Legs same colour as carapace; covered with pale hairs with a whitish sheen. Juveniles differ from adults in colour and the abdomen lacks a spotted appearance (Fig. 4).

Global distribution: In Southern Africa the species is recorded from five provinces in South Africa and Namibia.

Conservation measures: The species is sampled from the Fynbos, Savanna, Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes (Foord et al. 2011). Presently it is protected in the Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020b); Tswalu Game Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018); Goukamma Nature Reserve and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020c). There are no significant threats to the species, and due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

Figure 1. *Gandanameno fumosa* female from Namibia .

Figure 2. *Gandanameno fumosa* male from Namibia (Photo: A. Eichhoff).

Figure 3. *Gandanameno fumosa* small male (left) and female (right) .

Figure 4. *Gandanameno fumosa* juvenile.

Figure 5. Epigyne NCA 2020/554).

Figure 6. Leg spinules (From Miller et al. 2012).

Retreat web: The retreat of *G. fumosa* is frequently made in holes and openings in the rough bark of trees such as *Vachellia luederitzii* (Kalahari thorn) (Fig. 7). The retreat is usually made in the bottom third of the trees. It was also observed attached to rough boulders, with the retreat in a slit in the boulders. The retreat of the female consists of three parts: the flat catch web, anchor lines and the tunnel retreat.

The sheet-like catch web resembles a flat mosque tent. It is made of white cribellated silk. The size of the catch web (Fig. 10) varies depending on the size of the inhabitant; one measured 10 x 10 cm. The catch web is anchored to the substrate with numerous strong anchor lines (Figs 8 & 9). The catch web covers and opens into the retreat area, which consists of a number of tunnels. The size and number of tunnels depends on the age of the female.

The spider takes up position at the tunnel entrance with her front legs on the catch web, waiting for prey (Figs 10 & 11). This was seen during the day and at night. A female that caught a weevil pulled the insect into the tunnel before she started feeding.

Different insects have been identified from remnants left in the web, such as beetles, termites and ants (Fig. 12).

Figure 7. *Gandanameno fumosa* retreat.

Figure 8. *Gandanameno fumosa* showing the anchor lines.

Figure 9. *Gandanameno fumosa* showing the anchor line attachments (marked in yellow).

Figure 10. *Gandanameno fumosa* showing the catch web.

Figure 11. *Gandanameno fumosa* on the catch web.

Figure 12. Prey remains on the catch web.

In a *Ficus* tree a large nest was observed, consisting of dry leaves and silk (Fig. 13). When the nest was opened, ten different spiders were sampled, consisting of a female, an immature male and eight juveniles (Fig. 14). The egg sacs are deposited in the mother's nest (Fig. 15).

The male has his own retreat, about 30 X 15 mm in size, close to the female's nest. When the female dies her family seems to stay in close affinity, making their own webs close by (Fig. 16).

Figure 13. *Gandanameno fumosa* nest in tree.

Figure 14. Inhabitants of the nest . Figure 15. Egg sac in mother's nest .

Figure 16. Young spider new retreats close to the mother's nest..

CONCLUSION

Little is still known about the behaviour of many spiders, especially species of rare genera such as *Gandanameno*. This is the first record of the behaviour of *G. fumosa* in southern Africa. We now know they are active at night and make a catch web, feeding on a variety of insects. Juveniles tend to stay in close affinity to the female before building their own retreats close by.

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